

Systematic Review Protocol

Title

Comparison of Supervised Learning and Deep Learning Algorithms for Identifying Movement Intention in Individuals with Upper-Limb Amputation: A Systematic Review

Background / Rationale

Despite advances in myoelectric prosthetic control, accurately and efficiently identifying movement intention in individuals with upper-limb amputation remains a challenge. Traditional supervised learning algorithms and more recent deep learning approaches have been proposed, but their relative advantages in terms of accuracy and real-time performance have not been systematically compared. This review aims to synthesize current evidence, highlight gaps in the literature, and provide guidance for selecting algorithms that can improve the functionality and usability of upper-limb prostheses.

Objectives

The objective of this review is to compare traditional supervised learning algorithms (e.g., SVM, KNN, Random Forest) and deep learning algorithms (e.g., CNN, LSTM, MLP) in terms of accuracy and real-time applicability for identifying movement intention in individuals with upper-limb amputation. Specifically, the review will address the following question: **How do supervised learning algorithms compare with deep learning approaches regarding classification accuracy, latency, F1-score, and other performance metrics relevant to the control of myoelectric prostheses?**

Methods

Eligibility Criteria

Inclusion criteria:

- Studies including adults (≥ 18 years) with upper-limb amputation.
- Studies applying supervised learning algorithms (SVM, KNN, Random Forest) and/or deep learning algorithms (CNN, LSTM, MLP) for movement intention recognition.
- Studies reporting quantitative performance metrics such as accuracy, latency, F1-score, training or inference time, and error rate.
- Experimental, comparative, or technical validation studies.
- Publications in English or Spanish.
- Studies published between 2015 and 2025.

- Full-text articles available.

Exclusion criteria:

- Studies involving participants without upper-limb amputation.
- Studies not applying machine learning techniques.
- Studies not specifying or applying supervised or deep learning algorithms.
- Studies focused on unrelated applications (e.g., rehabilitation, diagnosis) not related to prosthetic control.
- Studies not reporting quantitative performance metrics.
- Review articles, conference abstracts without full data, editorials, or unpublished theses.
- Publications in languages other than English or Spanish.
- Articles without full-text availability.

Participants

Adults (18 years) with upper-limb amputation.

Interventions / Exposures

Deep learning algorithms (e.g., CNN, LSTM, MLP) applied to movement intention recognition.

Comparators

Traditional supervised learning algorithms (e.g., SVM, KNN, Random Forest).

Outcomes

Primary outcomes: classification accuracy and F1-score.

Secondary outcomes: latency, error rate, training/inference time.

Study Types

Experimental studies, comparative studies, and technical validation studies (non-randomised).

Search Strategy

Electronic databases: PubMed, Scopus, IEEE Xplore, and Web of Science. Search terms will combine PICO elements, for example: ("upper-limb amputation" OR "myoelectric prosthesis") AND ("supervised learning" OR "SVM" OR "KNN" OR "Random Forest")

AND ("deep learning" OR "CNN" OR "LSTM" OR "MLP") AND ("movement intention recognition" OR "motor intention").

Data Extraction and Management

Two reviewers will independently extract study characteristics, algorithms used, datasets, and performance metrics. Discrepancies will be resolved by consensus.

Risk of Bias

Risk of bias will be assessed using adapted technical evaluation checklists (e.g., reporting completeness, dataset description, algorithm reproducibility).

Data Synthesis

A narrative synthesis will be conducted. If sufficient homogeneity exists in datasets and metrics, a meta-analysis of performance outcomes will be considered.

Review Timeline

Start date: 24 August 2025.

Expected end date: 24 February 2026.